

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT: Energy crisis, especially fuel scarcity, is a significant hindrance to the effective operation of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. This study was examined the impact of fuel scarcity on the productivity of SMEs and assessed the effectiveness of government intervention strategies. A survey research design was adopted, using structured questionnaires administered across selected states in Nigeria. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including tables and charts. The authors discovered that fuel scarcity significantly affects the productivity of SMEs in the country, resulting in the decline of economic activities. The study concluded that fuel scarcity is a significant hindrance to the effective operation of SMEs and recommended that the Nigerian government, through its regulatory agencies, ensure that the sales and distribution of petroleum products, as well as the functionality of refineries, are properly monitored. It also recommended promoting the use of solar power as an alternative energy source to boost SME productivity and enhance economic development in the country.

KEYWORDS: Fuel Scarcity; The Greatest Happiness of the Greatest Number; Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs); Energy Crisis; Productivity; and Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

It is safe to say that one of the arguable difficult problems confronting Nigeria is premised on making fuel available for domestic consumption. Over the years, practical experiences have shown that Nigeria has been struggling to find a lasting panacea for the frequent fuel shortages in the country. It is necessary to highlight that successive government have adopted various schemes and strategies, such as yearly-turn around maintenance of refineries and importation of refined petrol into the country, among others to ensure fuel availability yet, the problem of fuel scarcity in Nigeria is far from over.

The current fuel shortage is a cause for concern and has hindered the operations of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). As Ikechukwu et al. (2025) noted, fuel scarcity is a worrisome and damaging issue because it affects virtually every sector of the economy. When fuel becomes scarce, the economy is pushed into an energy crisis that undermines national economic progress. The effects are far-reaching. Fuel scarcity raises transportation costs, reduces profit margins, disrupts supply chains, and increases the prices of goods in the market. Consequently, the productive activities of SMEs are significantly affected, as higher fuel costs translate into increased operational expenses and rising prices of commodities. In major commercial cities such as Lagos, Abuja, and Akwa Ibom State, many business owners have complained about the high cost of transportation. This situation often leads to reduced production capacity, price increases, job cuts, and, in some cases, business closures across various sectors of the economy (Pogoso et al., 2023).

Fuel being world commodity deserves to be given an undivided attention. It is so important that its nonavailability would portend serious problem for any country of the world, whether developed or developing. In the words of Abdulrasheed and Nurain (2024), without fuel, the world would, in no small time, be halted, lives would be made unbearably disgusting and unattractive. Factories would be greatly affected, airplanes would be made to standstill, people's homes and offices would also be affected. The relationship between fuel availability and SMEs is always positive. The productivity of SMEs is helplessly dependent on the availability and accessibility of fuel. SMEs' contribution to economic growth is not negligible, in actual fact, SMEs economic activities tell and show how, in most cases, healthy a country is for business or otherwise. Anytime there is decline in the supply of fuel and petrol or its price is hiked as a result of government policies, it usually culminate into losses, agitations, cries and hardship for SMEs (Vita, 2015). The reason is predicated upon the economic reality of chain effect of fuel scarcity.

Fuel scarcity in Nigeria has become a persistent and endemic challenge despite the existence of the policies and Dangote refinery, which has contributed to local refining in Nigeria, yet, the solution is still not in sight. Recently, Dangote refinery has adjusted its

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

pump prices in response to rising crude oil prices and global tensions involving Iran, the USA, and Israel (Daily Trust 11 March, 2026). Industry operators and economists have warned that if current global oil market conditions persist, petrol prices in Nigeria may continue to rise sharply, worsening the already challenging cost of living situation. Also, across several states, petrol prices have surged significantly, with many filling stations selling between N1,200 and N1,350 per litre, while some independent marketers suggest further increases are inevitable. This development has generated widespread concern among Nigerians, as rising fuel prices continue to increase transportation costs, food prices, and overall business expenses. The recurring nature of fuel shortages, coupled with rising pump prices, has led to increased operational costs, reduced productivity, supply chain disruptions, and, in many cases, business closures particularly those of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), which heavily depend on fuel for their operations. However, against the backdrop of the aforementioned challenges, this research's main objective is to examine the impact of Nigeria's fuel shortage on the productivity of SMEs in Nigeria. The study is conducted to fill a knowledge vacuum and provide insight into how businesses have been affected by the recent fuel crisis.

Furthermore, there is growing concern regarding the effectiveness of government policies in mitigating the adverse effects of fuel scarcity on SMEs. At the same time, SMEs are compelled to adopt internal coping mechanisms, the effectiveness of which remains largely under-examined. This situation raises critical questions which this paper seeks to ask as follows:

- i. what are the direct and indirect impacts of fuel scarcity on the productivity of SMEs in Nigeria?
- ii. how effective are government policies and interventions in mitigating the impact of fuel scarcity on SMEs?

Statement of the Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are stated in their null form

H₀₁: Fuel scarcity has no significant direct or indirect impact on the productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Government policies and interventions have no significant effect on mitigating the impact of fuel scarcity on SME's in Nigeria. This study is significant in several respects. First, it contributes to existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the impact of fuel scarcity on SME productivity in Nigeria. Second, it offers insights into the effectiveness of government policies and interventions aimed at mitigating the adverse effects of fuel scarcity, thereby informing policymakers on areas requiring improvement.

Third, the study highlights the coping strategies adopted by SMEs, which may serve as practical guides for business owners facing similar challenges. Additionally, the findings will be useful to researchers, academics, and students by expanding knowledge in the area of energy economics and SME development.

Finally, the study underscores the critical role of fuel availability in economic growth and business sustainability, thereby emphasizing the need for more efficient and sustainable energy policies in Nigeria.

The remaining parts of this study consists of 'Literature review section'; this spells out the conceptual framework, the theoretical review and the empirical review. The other section is 'Methodology section'; this section stipulates the data, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique and methods of data collection. The last section is 'Discussion and Analysis section'; this section specifies the descriptive analysis, descriptive analysis of the responses of the respondents.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explore the historical context of fuel issues in Nigeria, discusses the concepts of Scarcity, fuel scarcity and small and medium enterprises. It also reviews the theory that underpin the study and concludes with an empirical review of related literature.

2.1 Historical Context of Fuel Issues in Nigeria

Nigeria, Africa's largest oil producer, is currently grappling with a severe fuel scarcity that is affecting all sectors of its economy and exacerbating the hardships faced by its population. This crisis is not just a temporary inconvenience but a stark reflection of the systemic issues plaguing the nation's petroleum sector, policy failures to mentioned a few.

Nigeria's history with fuel scarcity dates back several decades, with periodic crises often triggered by global oil prices, governmental policies, and infrastructural problems. The 1970s oil boom brought wealth but also dependency on oil revenues, setting the stage for future economic vulnerabilities. In the 1980s and 1990s, Nigeria began to face recurring fuel shortages due to declining oil prices, corruption, and mismanagement. These shortages were exacerbated by the government's inconsistent policies on fuel subsidies, which have been both implemented and removed various times, leading to public unrest and economic instability.

Also, one of the triggers for the fuel scarcity especially from 2023 to date was the bold decision of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu to remove fuel subsidies, a longstanding policy intended to make fuel affordable for the majority of Nigerians. While subsidies have been beneficial for consumers, they have also strained government finances and encouraged wastage, smuggling, and inefficiency. The removal was aimed at reallocating funds to more productive sectors, but it led to a sudden and steep increase in fuel prices, catching many by surprise and without sufficient preparatory measures in place.

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

2.2 Scarcity

In its technical form, scarcity in economics connotes that the demand for goods and services is greater its availability. The unavailability of fuel always serves as a cog in the wheel of smooth running of SMEs in whatever case. In Nigeria, the scarcity of fuel has not only affected the smooth functioning of SMEs, but also affected other sectors in the country.

2.2.1. Fuel Scarcity

To describe the socio-economic reality of Nigeria without the word “scarcity” is incomplete. Scarcity in Nigeria from resources to growing capacity is rather a common thing as crisis in energy sector is usually brought about by scarcity. It is paradoxical to say that Nigeria, a country that has more than enough crude oil that can service its entire population and solve energy crisis, and still export to its neighboring countries is bedeviled with an ugly incidence of scarcity of fuel. Technically speaking, Nigeria should not be having a short fall in the fuel production as it has abundance of its by-product. Fuel scarcity is regrettably worrisome and always serves as a cog in the wheel of economic progress of any nation. The smooth running of businesses is at the mercy of the availability, affordability and accessibility of fuel.

Fuel Scarcity in Nigeria context, is having to go for crumbs in the midst of surplus. Most fuel scarcity in Nigeria is brought about by an attitude of unscrupulous individuals who are bound in milking the country dry at the expense of the masses. Fuel Scarcity is an absolute unavailability of premium motor spirit that makes the daily economic activities of people and businesses go smoothly well. Fuel Scarcity affects every sphere of the economy.

2.2.2 Drivers of Fuel Scarcity in Nigeria

As of March 2026, Nigeria is facing severe fuel scarcity and price hikes, with petrol prices surging to around ₦1,175 and ₦1,350 per litre, alongside warnings that prices could potentially reach ₦2,000 per litre (Daily Trust 11th March, 2026). This situation has greatly affected businesses, especially SMEs that depend heavily on fuel for daily operations. Over time, the causes of gasoline shortage in Nigeria have been widely researched and documented with some of the factors explained as follows:

a. Price Deregulation and Naira Devaluation: Price deregulation and the removal of fuel subsidy, alongside the adoption of a floating exchange rate system, have made fuel imports significantly more expensive. Since Nigeria still relies heavily on imported refined petroleum products, the depreciation of the naira against major foreign currencies (especially the US dollar) directly increases the landing cost of fuel.

For instance, when Nigeria currency(naira) weakens, it therefore means that marketers will need more naira to purchase the same quantity of fuel in dollars. This cost will definitely be transferred to consumers in the form of higher pump prices. Also, when one critically looked at Nigeria’ from post-subsidy removal period, one will released that fuel prices have been more than doubled, contributing significantly to inflation (even though it fluctuates) and increased cost of production for businesses.

b. Logistics and Infrastructure Constraints: The distribution of petroleum products across Nigeria is another critical factor that has made it difficult to have consistent fuel supply across regions. This nation depend solidly on road transport (tankers) due to the near absence of functional pipelines and rail systems for fuel distribution. This reliance on road transportation leads to frequent delays caused by poor road conditions, traffic congestion, and accidents. Additionally, periodic strikes by petroleum sector unions such as NUPENG and PENGASSAN often disrupt fuel supply chains nationwide(Pogoso et al., 2023). These disruptions create artificial shortages even when fuel is available at depots.

c. Foreign Exchange Scarcity: Foreign exchange scarcity remains a major constraint in Nigeria’s downstream petroleum sector. Marketers often struggle to secure sufficient US dollars required for importing refined petroleum products. Even local refining efforts are not immune to this challenge. For example, the Dangote Refinery, although operational, still requires foreign exchange to procure crude oil from international markets to supplement domestic supply. This dependence on foreign currency creates a bottleneck in fuel production and supply, thereby contributing to scarcity and rising prices which affect the operations of small and medium businesses(Vincent, 2022).

d. Refinery Supply Chain Challenges: The refinery supply chain in Nigeria is characterized by high operational costs and inefficiencies. Local refineries, particularly the Dangote Refinery, source crude oil at international market prices. This implies that domestic fuel prices are influenced by global oil price fluctuations rather than local production advantages. In addition, factors such as high taxes and duties, inadequate infrastructure, and limited refining capacity further increase the cost of production. Nigeria’s refining capacity has historically been insufficient, forcing reliance on imports. According to Musa, (2022), despite Nigeria being a major crude oil producer, the absence of adequate downstream facilities for refining and storage has resulted in persistent fuel shortages and price volatility.

e. Hoarding, Corruption, and Distribution Bottlenecks : Hoarding of petroleum products by marketers in anticipation of price increases is another major cause of artificial scarcity. This practice reduces the quantity of fuel available in the market, thereby driving up prices. Corruption and poor management within the petroleum sector also contribute significantly to the problem. Issues such as diversion of fuel, fraudulent practices by marketers, and weak regulatory enforcement worsen the situation. Additionally,

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

oil pipeline vandalism disrupts the transportation of crude oil to refineries and finished products to depots, further aggravating supply shortages (Abeng et al., 2022).

2.2.3 Economic and Social Impacts of Fuel Scarcity

The persistent fuel scarcity in Nigeria has far-reaching economic and social consequences, including:

i. High Inflation: The surge in fuel prices directly increases transportation costs, which in turn raises the prices of goods and services. Since fuel is a major input in production and distribution, higher fuel costs translate into higher food prices and general inflation. Recent economic data in Nigeria show a strong correlation between fuel price increases and rising inflation rates.

ii. Business Disruption: Many small and medium enterprises face significantly higher operating expenses due to increased fuel costs. Businesses that rely on generators for electricity are particularly affected. As a result, some SMEs are forced to scale down operations, reduce staff, or shut down entirely.

iii. Reduced Purchasing Power: The purchasing power of citizens has weakened considerably as incomes remain relatively constant while the cost of living continues to rise. Many individuals can no longer afford basic transportation, leading to reduced economic participation and lower overall demand in the economy.

2.2.4 Solutions to fuel scarcity in Nigeria

To address fuel scarcity comprehensively, the Nigerian government needs to implement a multi-faceted approach that targets the root causes while prioritizing long-term sustainability. Here are some potential solutions:

a. Revamping Refineries: The existing refineries must undergo extensive rehabilitation and modernization. Investment in new technologies, skilled personnel, and improved management practices would enhance refining capacity and reduce reliance on imported fuel.

b. Diversifying Energy Sources: Nigeria must explore alternative energy sources such as renewable energy, including, CNG, solar and wind power. Diversification would reduce dependence on fossil fuels and create additional sources of energy for various sectors, lessening the pressure on the fuel supply system.

c. Strengthening Pipeline Security: Effective security measures must be put in place to safeguard pipelines against vandalism and illegal tapping. Collaborating with local communities and law enforcement agencies can help in curbing these criminal activities, ensuring a continuous supply of fuel across the country.

d. Promoting Transparency and Accountability: Combating corruption requires increased transparency and accountability in the petroleum industry. Implementing strong governance frameworks, monitoring mechanisms, and stricter penalties for corrupt practices are crucial towards ensuring that resources meant for infrastructure development and maintenance are not misappropriated.

e. Infrastructure Development: Upgrading storage facilities, increasing filling stations, and improving transportation networks would enhance fuel distribution efficiency. Investments in infrastructure would ensure a steady and reliable supply of fuel to all regions across Nigeria.

2.3 Small and Medium Enterprises

Big business organizations are built on small and medium enterprises (SMEs); thriving SMEs, among many other things, are the backbone of developed countries of the world because SMEs have an inherent economic strength to trigger aggregate demand and increase the wealth of a nation (Okijie and Effiong, 2024). To attain socio-economic development, almost developed countries have charted a well-supervised plan to boost and encourage the operational economic activities of SMEs. It is impossible to overstate the importance of the experiences of developed countries in relation to the roles played by SMEs, in particular among the emerging nations like Nigeria or Less Developed Countries (LDCs).

Ogunbiyi, (2021) opined that the fact that almost all countries that have focused on the SMEs sector and ensured its vibrancy have succeeded in the significant reduction and its attendant enhancement in the quality and standard of living, reduction in the crime rate, increase in per capita income as well as rapid growth in GDP among other positive effects, has earned SMEs the moniker “engine of growth”. In conceptualizing SMEs, it is seen as an organization that its sole survival and vibrancy depend on energy power; energy crisis and other gasoline shortage problems always hamper on the productivity of SMEs. Hence, a country willing to spark economic growth via SMEs must have a robust and functional energy and gasoline reserves.

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are independent, non-subsidiary businesses characterized by a limited number of employees, with definitions varying across countries (Awulu et al., 2025). The European Union (EU) defines SMEs as firms employing fewer than 250 people with an annual turnover not exceeding 50 million euros (European Commission, 2003). Similarly, small enterprises employ 1-49 people, while medium enterprises employ 50–249 people (Prenaj & Ismajli, 2018), consistent with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2005).

In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) defines SMEs as businesses with annual turnover not exceeding five hundred thousand naira (Adedipe, 2023). Despite definitional differences, SMEs are widely acknowledged as key drivers of economic development, accounting for about 90% of businesses and over 50% of global employment, and contributing up to 40% of GDP in emerging economies (IFC, 2017; World Bank, 2022a, 2022b). SMEs play a vital role in innovation, industrial development, and

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

employment generation. In Nigeria, they are regarded as the engine of industrial transformation due to their flexibility and low capital requirements (Etuk et al., 2014).

2.3.1 Productivity of SMEs in Nigeria and the Impact of Fuel Scarcity

Productivity of SMEs refers to the efficiency with which factors of production such as labour, capital, energy, and technology are used to generate output. It is commonly measured as the ratio of output to input and serves as a key indicator of business performance, profitability, and sustainability. In the Nigerian context, SME productivity is critical to economic growth, given that SMEs account for about 90% of businesses, contribute significantly to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and provide a substantial share of employment (International Finance Corporation (World Bank, 2022a).

In Nigeria, SMEs are widely regarded as the backbone of the economy. They account for about **96% of businesses, contribute approximately 48% to Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and provide about 84% of employment**. This shows that the productivity of SMEs is directly linked to national economic performance, job creation, and poverty reduction. When SMEs perform efficiently, the economy grows; when their productivity declines, the entire economy is affected (Etuk et al., 2014).

Fuel crisis, which has become a monster in Nigeria that usually undermines SME productivity through multiple channels. First, it increases the cost of production, as SMEs spend more on fuel for generators and transportation (Ikechukwu et al., 2025). Second, it reduces output and production capacity, as businesses cannot operate efficiently without adequate fuel supply. Third, fuel scarcity disrupts supply chains, leading to delays in production and distribution (Pogason et al., 2023). It also reduces profitability, weakens financial stability, and limits business expansion.

Additionally, fuel unavailability often affect SME's operations leading to scaling down operations and subsequent reduction in workforce which contributes to unemployment (Adedipe, 2023). Fuel scarcity also drives inflation, reduces purchasing power, and lowers demand for goods and services, further constraining SME productivity. Although SMEs adopt coping strategies such as cost-cutting and reduced production, these measures limit long-term growth and competitiveness (Mekwunye, 2018).

2.4. Theoretical Review

This study is built on the theoretical foundation of Jeremy Bentham and John Stuart Mill: "the greatest happiness of the greatest number". Both proponents belonged to the utilitarian school. The fundamental tenet of this theory is that everyone deserves happiness, which can be defined as the excess of pleasure over suffering. The number of people affected when dealing with a group is another consideration when weighing the benefits against the costs, taking into account the number of people affected, and determining whether the proposed law will produce the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people. The theory aptly explains why the Nigerian petrol shortage did not result in the greatest happiness for the largest amount of people. Instead, the lack of fuel has put the populace through unnecessary hardship and halted the country's growth by slowing down the productivity of SME's. This theory also describes the narrative of fuel scarcity escapades in Nigeria; whenever there is a fuel scarcity, the most affected part is SME's and their productivity level. To think Nigeria is an oil-rich country and still suffers fuel scarcity and unavailability is paradoxically sickening and appalling, and this ugly trend has really affected the economic activities of sector which has inherent capacity to drive growth and validate almost macroeconomic benefits (Rwamparagi et al., 2025).

2.5 Empirical Review of Related Literature

There are quite a number of empirical research on fuel scarcity, particularly in Nigeria, and several researchers have made fruitful attempts which this study has reviewed. They are as follows:

Ikechukwu et al., (2025) conducted a study on how SMEs were affected by the fuel subsidy removal and scarcity in Anambra state of Nigeria. The empirical findings showed that fuel subsidy removal had a significant impact on the cost of living and doing business in Awka, Anambra State. The findings are not appropriate to be classified as the generic result in all of the states of federation. Edirimumi and Liyanagamage, (2024) carried out a study on mediating energy management on SMEs during the power crisis in Sri Lanka using quantitative methods, the study analyzed the survey data of 143 SMEs selected through sampling in Sri Lanka. The results showed that there is significant negative impact of energy crisis, showing halted productive activities and nosedived employment.

In Indonesia, Wijaya et al., (2022) investigated the importance of fuel and energy consumptions on the productivity of MSMEs industries. The empirical finding revealed that the shortage and unavailability of energy and fuel had insignificant effect on the productive activities of MSMEs in Indonesia as they opted for an alternative source of energy.

Akpan and Nnamseh (2014) carried out a study in Akwa Ibom State with the purpose of establishing the efficacy of strategic management strategy in the management of petrol scarcity in Nigeria. Participants in the survey included 150 local petroleum consumers, 7,792 members of the National Union of Petroleum and Natural Gas Workers (NUPENG), and members of the Independents Petroleum Marketers Association of Nigeria (IPMAN). The sample size was 396 respondents, and questionnaires and secondary data were used as data gathering tools. According to the findings, Nigeria's fuel shortage was caused by a number of factors, including excessive corruption and poor management, vandalism of oil pipelines, a lack of refineries, smuggling and diversion, hoarding, administrative bottlenecks and legal restrictions, a lack of manpower, and fuel subsidies. It also suggested that

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

slowdown of economic growth, hike in transit fare were the key related risk of shortage, and small and medium enterprises were greatly affected as their daily economic activities were slowed down.

In Sudan, Mai et al., (2016) undertook a study on the causes, impacts and solutions to the sporadic fuel shortage in the study area. The study used data from Nile Petroleum Corporation (NilePet), Customs Directorate, fuel stations and interviews with oil industry, Petroleum Ministry, and National Security representatives. The empirical results reveal that hard currency shortage, high taxes and duties, absence of refineries and depots were the causes of the fuel scarcity. The study did not clearly specify the exact impact on small and medium enterprises.

Alaba and Agbalajobi, (2014) empirically evaluated the performance of private refineries and depots in the distribution of petroleum products in Lagos metropolis. The sample size was 150. Questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection, which was administered on ninety (90) randomly selected five major and ten independent private depots, whilst sixty (60) were distributed to the public. The results showed that corruption, vandalization, poor performance of refineries and government policies were responsible for petrol scarcity in Nigeria.

Ayakwah and Mohammed (2014) explored on fuel price adjustments and the growth of SMEs in New Juaben Municipality of Ghana. The study used a social survey method with a sample size of 204 and a purposive sampling was used to get information from respondents. The empirical results showed that increases in fuel price results in increases in transportation costs, raw materials costs, capital costs and other costs. The result of the Key informant interviews conducted by the study showed that, approximately 75% of SMEs in the New Juaben Municipality complained when price of fuel is adjusted upwards it usually brought about reduction in output and subsequent slow in business and productivity.

In the same vein, Ahmed and Halima, (2013) did a study on fuel scarcity and its effect on the economy. The study sample comprised of 86 small scale businesses in the Bauchi Metropolis. The major instrument of data collection was secondary sources. The ex-post facto research design was used and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The empirical results of the study showed that fuel scarcity is a re-occurring menace that unfavorably affect virtually all sectors of the Nigerian economy. Also, the study revealed that when there is a fuel scarcity, the country's revenue nosedives.

NilePet, Customs Directorate, gas stations, and interviews with the oil industry, Petroleum Ministry, and National Security representatives were all utilized in the study Umar and Umar (2013) and Siddig et al. (2014) noted that Nigeria's subsidy regime distorts fiscal planning, encourages inefficient consumption, and increases inequality as richer households benefit more. Siddig et al. (2014) further showed that subsidy reduction increases the GDP and reduces household income. It has also been shown that fuel subsidy removal in Nigeria could cause inflation and reduce economic welfare (Adenikinju, 2009); hurt economic growth and reduce household income (Ocheni, 2015); and make firms less competitive (Bazilian and Onyeji, 2012). These studies applied either the computable general equilibrium model (Siddig et al., 2014; Adenikinju, 2009) or the analysis of survey data (Ocheni, 2015). The findings pointed to a lack of available hard money, excessive taxes and levies, a lack of refineries and depots, rising demand for oil from electricity generators and consumers, and inefficient energy use as root reasons for the fuel shortfall. Corruption and a lack of fair market controls were also blamed for the rising costs of food and other necessities as well as the decline in productivity and widening income gap.

From the reviewed literature, it is observed that empirical studies that have analyzed the impact of fuel scarcity on SMEs in Nigeria, in all the states of the federation is still needed in the literature as most studies analyzed the impact of fuel scarcity on SMEs in some selected states of the federation in Nigeria. This study is justified and important by looking at the holistic impact of fuel scarcity on SMEs in Nigeria.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research will involve both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Qualitative research methods such as focus groups, interviews, and case studies will be used to obtain a better understanding of the impact of fuel scarcity on SME productivity in Nigeria. Quantitative research methods such as surveys and statistical analysis will be used to collect data on the same.

3.1 Population of the study

As it was not feasible to create a full population survey, we used Stratified Sampling (SS) to select our evaluation population. Stratified Sampling involves dividing the population into sub-populations that may differ in many ways. For this study, we used the states as the subgroups. The states are the strata and a simple random sampling was conducted in each state. Sample size for each state was chosen based on the total population of the state in comparison with the expected sample size of the overall survey.

Figure 1: Number of Response by State

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

Figure 1: Number of Response by State
Source: Field Survey, 2023

From the chart above, we have the highest number of respondents from **AKWA IBOM STATE** with **300 responses (4% of the total response)** and the least response from **KASTINA STATE** with **78 responses (1% of the total response)**.

Figure 2: Respondents' Business Type Respondents Business Type

The survey targeted SMEs, the chart above is a graphical representation of the prominent SME's type of those that participated in the survey. From the chart **44.2 percent** of the respondents are into **RETAIL/WHOLESALE TRADING** which is the highest SME's type under the survey.

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

Figure 3: Respondents' Years of Business Establishment

This discusses the number of years an average owner of SME's has been operating business during and after scarcity of fuel. The internal mechanism to mitigate and cushion the effect of fuel scarcity can be empirically known from years of establishment by the owners of SME's

From the chart above, **majority** of the businesses under study has been in existence for **at least 5 years** since establishment.

Figure 4: Number of Members of the Staff

Number of Members of the Staff

This number of the members of staff connotes the operational strength of SMEs in Nigeria. In the mainstream economic theory and holding all other factors constant, a high number of the members of staff will increase the average variable cost, and fuel scarcity may downsize it.

From the survey **71 percent** of the SMEs under study have **below 10 staffs** and 24 percent have between 11 to 50 members of the staff

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

Figure 5: Energy Sources Being Used by SMEs
Source: Field Survey, 2023

Petrol, fondly called PMS in Nigeria is largely used by the owners of SMEs. Though, it is fossil fuels but informal space of Nigeria's macroeconomic structure needs it for day-to-day running of their business concern.

From the chart above, it is clear that **PETROL** is a major source of energy used by SMEs. From the survey **above 70 percent** of the respondent uses petrol as energy source.

Figure 6: Frequency of the Usage of Fuel

This empirically shows that fuel is very pivotal and integral for the smooth running of SMEs business activities in Nigeria. The scarcity and inaccessibility of fuel crumbles and renders the business activities of SMEs futile and unproductive.

How often Fuel is been Purchased

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From the survey fuel is purchased more on a **daily** base with **59 percent** response rate.

3.2 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique was employed in the selection process since the major targets were those SMEs operating in Nigeria and their customers. A stratified sampling technique was used because the managers and owners were willing to give all the needed information. Questionnaires were administered through-out the states of the federation. In this study, sample size and the technique is seemed as the same owing to the empirical fact that the study was carried out to analyze the effect of fuel scarcity on all the Small and Medium Enterprises in all the states of the federation.

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

3.3 Methods of Data Collection

The study relied on primary data. Primary data are those which are firsthand information and often referred to as original data. The study used questionnaires and focused group discussions and interviews to collect data, a set of questionnaires was designed, in line with the posited research questions.

3.4 Procedure for Data Analysis and Model Specification

To analyze the collected and collated data, the study employed simple descriptive statistics, comprising of pie charts and frequency tables.

4.0 DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

This section presents and analyses the data collected through the questionnaire. The descriptive tools used include frequency tables and percentages values. More so, the descriptive analysis concentrated on the use of frequency by examining the responses of all the respondents (economic agents) in all the states of the federation.

4.1 Descriptive Analysis of the Response of Respondents

Table 1: H₀₁: Fuel scarcity has no significant direct or indirect impact on the productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) in Nigeria.

We explored several items as significant problems faced by companies during the fuel scarcity period, the items were selected from a focus group discussion. The items were now included into the questionnaire to ascertain the level of impact of these items on SME's during the fuel scarcity period. From the percentage of the responses, it is clear that the items explored are significant problems faced by SME's during the fuel scarcity period. The direct impact of fuel scarcity on SMEs' productivity is linked to their inability to increase their respective business operations; the impact is directly proportional to the running of the business concern, and the indirect effect is zoomed up into the negative effect on their productivity.

Furthermore, the RII result ranked **ITEM I** as the most significant of all items which means one of the major problems faced by companies during the fuel scarcity during was **reduction in business operations**.

Table 1: Problems faced by SME's during fuel scarcity as arranged by RII
Significant Problems faced by Companies during the Fuel Scarcity

ITEMS	YES	NO	RII
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	
1 The fuel Scarcity reduces your business operation	6808 (92%)	615 (8%)	0.96
2 Financial losses have been incurred due to fuel scarcity	6529 (88%)	894 (12%)	0.94
3 Affected the morale of staff	6165 (83%)	1258 (17%)	0.92
4 Reduction of demand for my products and/or services	5711 (77%)	1712 (23%)	0.88
5 Difficulty in my company's ability to deliver services and/or products to customers	6378 (86%)	1045 (14%)	0.93
6 Difficulty to acquire the supplies and/or services required to produce my products and/or deliver my services	6296 (85%)	1127 (15%)	0.92
7 Difficulty in paying staff salaries and other fixed business costs, such as rent or utilities	5881 (79%)	1542 (21%)	0.90
8 Slow the flow of business process	6555 (88%)	868 (12%)	0.94
9 Fuel scarcity affect the productivity of your business	6706 (90%)	717 (10%)	0.95

Note 1: RII is Relative Importance Index used to weigh and rank responses.

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

Figure 7: Frequency of truancy and irregularity
Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The figure shows the number of times employees of SMEs absent from work due to difficulties in accessing transport service or nay means of conveyance from their respective domains to their place of work.

From the graph above, it shows that employees were still committed to work during the period of fuel scarcity. Majority of the employee irregularity was below 20%. This can be alluded to the fact that SME's businesses are closed and not functioning to their full capacity due to employees' irregularity. The figure also shows the indirect effect of fuel scarcity on SME's productivity in Nigeria.

Percentage of Employee irregularity due to Fuel scarcity

Table 2. H0₁: Fuel scarcity has no significant impact on the productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises (SME's) in Nigeria.

We explored several measures as impacts of the fuel scarcity on business productivity, these measures were selected from a focus group discussion. The measures were included to the questionnaire to ascertain the level of impact of these measures on SME's productivity.

From the percentage of the responses, it is clear that all measures explored are significant negative impact on business productivity during the fuel scarcity period.

Furthermore, the RII result there was an undeniable negative impact of the fuel scarcity on business productivity. The financial situation of the company was a major placed that was affected by the fuel scarcity.

Table 2: Measures of Impact of the Fuel Scarcity of Business Productivity

MEASURES	Large Negative impact Frequency (%)	Somewhat Negative Impact Frequency (%)	No Impact Frequency (%)	Somewhat Positive Impact Frequency (%)	Large Positive Impact Frequency (%)	RII
1 Overall impact on your business	4422	2622	255	43	81	0.90
2 Impact on Financial Situation of your business	3938	2968	394	43	80	0.89
3 Impact on channels for distribution of your products and services to customer	4002	2710	522	70	119	0.88
4 Impact on customer demand for your product or services	3650	2769	744	70	190	0.86
5 Impact on suppliers and supply chains	3877	2750	581	65	150	0.87

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

6	Impact on input and output of workers	3828	2808	553	80	154	0.87
7	Did the fuel subsidy impact positively or negatively on your business profitability?	4240	2376	460	121	226	0.88

Note 1: RII is Relative Importance Index used to weigh and rank responses.

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 3: H₀₂: Government policies and interventions have no significant effect on mitigating the impact of fuel scarcity on SME's in Nigeria.

The table is a list of possible recommendations to help curd the effect of the scarcity on business productivity. These measures are feed backs from the respondents on the role of government in handling the issue of fuel scarcity.

From the result of the RII, Government intervention in the improvement of availability of fuel for businesses and putting measures in place to reduce the effect of fuel scarcity ranked as the top recommendations.

Table 3: Likely Measures to Curb Future Fuel Scarcity

MEASURES	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	RII
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	
1 Government intervention is necessary to improve the availability of fuel for businesses.	5292 (71.3%)	1879 (25.3%)	176 (2.4%)	49 (0.7%)	27 (0.4%)	0.93
2 There is need to put measures in place in order to reduce the effect of fuel scarcity on businesses.	4659 (62.8%)	2499 (33.7%)	184 (2.5%)	59 (0.8%)	22 (0.3%)	0.92
3 Lack of operational refineries contributes to fuel scarcity in Nigeria.	4878 (65.7%)	2110 (28.4%)	300 (4%)	91 (1.2%)	44 (0.6%)	0.91
4 Current efforts of government to control the fuel scarcity are adequate.	2560 (34.5%)	1974 (26.6%)	1005 (13.5%)	822 (11.1%)	1062 (14.3%)	0.71
5 Renewable energy sources (solar, inverter) are good alternative to fuel.	3681 (49.6%)	2485 (33.5%)	656 (8.8%)	354 (4.8%)	247 (3.3%)	0.84
6 Fuel Subsidy Removal	2651 (35.7%)	2047 (27.6%)	1286 (17.3%)	713 (9.6%)	726 (9.8%)	0.74
7 Setting up Task Force on Petroleum Product Monitoring	4266 (57.5%)	2276 (30.7%)	484 (6.5%)	290 (3.9%)	107 (1.4%)	0.88

Note 1: RII is Relative Importance Index used to weigh and rank responses.

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Figure 8: Graphical representation of the measures to mitigate against future occurrence of fuel scarcity
Graphical Representation of Respondents Opinion

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This study examined the impact of fuel scarcity on the productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The study was premised on the understanding that energy, particularly fuel, plays an indispensable role in the smooth running of business activities.

Findings from the analysis revealed a strong linkage between fuel availability and SME operations. The results, as indicated by the Relative Importance Index (RII), showed that fuel scarcity significantly contributed to low economic activities and reduced business operations among SMEs.

The study further revealed that SMEs across different regions, including Akwa Ibom State in the Niger Delta, were adversely affected by fuel shortages despite the region's oil-producing status. This indicates that fuel scarcity is a nationwide structural issue rather than a regional problem.

In addition, the findings showed that fuel scarcity negatively affected the financial capacity of SMEs. Cash flows were disrupted, operating costs increased, and daily business activities which drive aggregate demand were significantly constrained. The study also found that fuel shortages led to reduced workforce productivity, including employee absenteeism and declining operational efficiency.

5.2 CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concludes that there is a significant relationship between fuel scarcity and the business operations of SMEs in Nigeria. Fuel, as an indispensable source of energy, remains central to the productivity and sustainability of SMEs.

The study established that fuel scarcity is injurious and harmful to commercial operations, as it leads to reduced productivity, increased operational costs, and declining business performance. The overall effect extends beyond individual businesses to the broader economy, affecting income generation, employment, and economic stability.

Furthermore, the findings align with previous studies such as Vincent (2023) and Ugwu (2016), which confirmed that persistent fuel shortages have measurable negative impacts on business performance in Nigeria.

It is therefore evident that addressing fuel scarcity is critical to enhancing SME productivity and promoting sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

5.3 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Improvement of Refinery Operations:

The government of Nigeria should take proactive steps to improve fuel scarcity in Nigeria by ensuring that existing refineries are properly maintained and managed, as well as building new ones where necessary. The various stakeholders, such as NNPL, should ensure that strategic management is employed to improve fuel supply in Nigeria.

2. Strengthening Monitoring and Regulation:

The various levels of government, from federal to state and then local, should ensure that monitoring committees are set up to monitor fuel distribution and sales in Nigeria. The illegality associated with fuel distribution should be addressed by ensuring that regulations are enforced.

3. Promotion of Alternative Energy Sources:

The use of alternative forms of energy, such as solar energy, should be encouraged in Nigeria to cushion the effect of fuel scarcity, particularly for SMEs in Nigeria.

5.4 Implications of the Study

The implications of this study's findings have significant economic and policy implications. The study affirms the importance of fuel in supporting the operations of SMEs and the effects of energy instability on productivity and economic activities.

It also indicates structural inefficiencies in Nigeria's petroleum industry, considering that some parts of the country, which are oil-producing, face fuel scarcity. Moreover, the financial burden on SMEs indicates macroeconomic consequences, including lower aggregate demand, higher levels of unemployment, and lower economic growth.

These implications underscore the need for effective energy policies and sustainable energy options in Nigeria.

5.5 Contribution to Knowledge

This research contributes to the existing body of knowledge in the following ways: First and foremost, this research contributes to existing knowledge by offering empirical evidence on the link between fuel scarcity and SME productivity in Nigeria.

Secondly, this research makes use of the Relative Importance Index (RII) to measure the extent of the impact of fuel scarcity on SME productivity, thereby offering a quantitative dimension to the analysis.

Impact of Fuel Scarcity on the Productivity of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria

Thirdly, it contributes to the broader discourse on energy economics and SME development in developing countries, particularly Nigeria.

Lastly, this research contributes to existing knowledge by offering deeper insights into the effects of fuel scarcity on SME financial flows and productivity.

5.6 Areas for Further Research

Based on the limitations and findings of this study, the following are some of the possible research directions that may be considered in the future:

1. Comparative studies may be carried out in various regions or sectors to find the differences in the impact of fuel scarcity.
2. Studies may be conducted to find the long-run impact of fuel scarcity on the growth and survival of SMEs.
3. Studies may be carried out to find the impact of the use of alternate energy sources like solar energy in reducing the impact of fuel scarcity.
4. Studies may be carried out using advanced econometric techniques to find the impact of government policies and reforms in improving the supply of energy.
5. Studies may be carried out using a wider population to generalize the research findings.

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